

Automatic Plant Monitoring

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Abstract-Taking care of plants can be largely time consuming. Missing even a small scheduled task for the plant can result in the drying up of the plant and even its death. Another big problem is to put the plant pot at a place where it gets maximum sunlight. This is a big problem in houses (apartments) where the place with maximum sunlight shifts throughout the day and it's very tiring to shift the plant, time-to-time to those places. Watering the plant by checking the amount of moisture in the soil of the pot is another very important and time-consuming task. Automating all these processes or tasks can result in a huge work reduction and time saving for the owner and makes sure that the plant stays alive and healthy. This is the main goal of this project. The smart plant pot can do all the above tasks automatically, without needing any human intervention.

Key Words: *plant pots, IOT, Arduino, Automation, plant nourishment*

1. INTRODUCTION

Caring for plants can take a lot of time, moreover it is not uncommon for one plant to be treated more than one plant. Missing even a small scheduled task for the plant can result in the plant drying out and even its death. Trivial things like forgetting to water the plants and monitoring how the humidity level of the plants is very troublesome. This is a common problem for people who are already too busy with other things. How would it feel if plants could take care of themselves?

Automating all these processes or tasks can result in a huge work reduction and time saving for the owner and makes sure that the plant stays alive and healthy.

This is the main goal of this project. Smart plant pots can perform certain tasks automatically, making our work easier. The plant pot will be assisted by a sensor that can measure the level of moisture in the soil, whether dry or wet, if it needs water, it will automatically be channeled through a water pump. Some data will also be logged in the linked database, while also informing the owner of this. This is all done automatically by the pot without the need for human intervention

2. HARDWARE SYSTEM

2.1 Node MCU

MCU nodes are microchips equipped with wi-fi capabilities, analog pins, digital pins, and serial communication protocols. It can connect to wi-fi. In this project it is used to post owner updates on what the potted plants are doing at the moment and what their status is. Equipped with ESP8266 wifi chip. This development chip can be programmed using Arduino IDE

2.1 DHT11

The DHT11 sensor is a sensor module that functions to sense temperature and humidity objects that have an analog voltage output that can be further processed using a microcontroller. This sensor module is classified as a resistive element such as a temperature measuring device such as an NTC.

2.2 Relay

The relay module is a device that operates based on electromagnetic principles to move the contactor to move the ON position to OFF or vice versa by utilizing electric power. This closed and open event of the contactor occurs due to the effect of magnetic induction arising from the electric induction coil. The most basic difference between a relay and a switch is when it is moved from the ON position to the OFF position. The relay performs the transfer automatically with an electric current, while the switch is done manually.

2.3 Soil Moisture Sensor

This sensor senses the amount of moisture in the soil of the plant and signals Arduino the moisture levels at various points. The Arduino observes these moisture levels and it responds whenever the moisture levels are below a certain threshold value. This threshold is hardcoded into the program fed to the Arduino. Whenever the moisture levels reach below the threshold, Arduino turns the motors on and takes the plant pot to the nearest water station.

2.4 Water Level Sensor

The water sensor or water level sensor is used to detect water leakage, rainfall, tank overflow, or to measure the water level.

2.5 Waterpump

Water pump is a device capable of generating a flow of liquid using kinetic energy. Therefore, it has some basic elements:

- Tickets: where the liquid is absorbed.
- Motor + Propeller: the one in charge of generating the kinetic energy that extracts the water from the inlet and sends it through the outlet.
- Check-out: it is the inlet where the liquid propelled by the power of the water pump will come out.

3. SOFTWARE USED

3.1 Visual Studio Code

In visual studio code, it is useful for creating websites, fetching data from arduino and sending it to my sql, as well as retrieving data from my sql and sending it to android studio.

3.2 Arduino IDE

In the Arduino IDE, to program the microcontroller so that it can run according to the specified scheme

3.3 Android Studio

Android studio, in our project is used to display android application based data.

4. DATABASE USED

MySQL

In mysql, the place to store and process our project data.

5. HOW IT WORKS

This is what our system can do, Arduino IDE is used to run the program esp8266 and so on, and later the results of this program are sent to the mysql database using php, then to display it on the website page we use visual studio code, where the website functions to display data and read data with diagrams line, and through this visual studio code, android studio can also retrieve data from the mysql database.

Next our Plant Pot can read sensor value, moisture value, water level, voltage, humidity and temperature. The sensor value aims to read the voltage from the sensor which will be in the form of an integer, then moisture is useful for reading whether the soil is dry or still wet, if it is still wet it will send digital pin 0 while if it is dry it will send digital pin 1 which later will be processed to turn on the water pump relay so that the water pump can run, while for the water level it is used to measure whether the water capacity place is still filled or not, while for voltage it is useful for measuring the voltage obtained and will later be changed to measure the value of the water level, while humidity is used to measure the value of humidity around the plant, and just like humidity, temperature is also used to measure the temperature value around the plant, and all this data will be read every minute.

FLOWCHART ARDUINO IDE

FLOWCHART WEBSITE

FLOWCHART DATABASE

FLOWCHART SMARTPHONE

6. SYSTEM INTERFACE & RESULTS

Here is what the Automatic Plant Monitoring system interface looks like:

Here's the monitoring display via the website when it's opened on a PC.

Here's the monitoring display via the website when it's opened on a Smartphone.

In this website we can monitor through the available line charts which will be updated every minute.

Here's the monitoring display via android. In monitoring via Android, only data is available in the form of numbers.

Here is what the Automatic Plant Monitoring system looks like. For results, as we discussed earlier in the introduction, the soil moisture sensor will read the soil moisture, then if it is concluded that the soil is dry and requires water intake, the water will automatically be channeled by a water pump which is turned on by a relay.

CONCLUSION

In this conclusion section, we conclude several things, including the following::

1. It can be concluded that Automatic Plant Monitoring can make it easier for someone to take care of and maintain their plants, this system is very useful for people who are busy but really love their plants.

2. This system can only monitor the status of soil moisture, so from there if you feel the soil moisture is dry, the water will be channeled for plant fertility.
3. The updated data can be monitored via the website and also through the Android application, in the form of a line chart and a list of data
4. The drawback of this system is that it does not help plants if one day the plants need UV light or sunlight.

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